

Situational Issues and Availability of Agricultural Products in Nigeria (A Study of Food Availability in South-East, Nigeria)

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Abstract: The study examined the impact of situational issues on the availability of agricultural products with particular reference to agricultural food in south east Nigeria. Such situational issues that formed the independent variables of the study are covid-19 pandemic, herdsmen attack on farmers and IPOB sit-at-home order. The study tried to establish the effect of these variables on the availability of agricultural food in South East Nigeria. The research instrument used for the study is questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered on those that were affected by these situations studied. The sample size for the study was 246 and was determined using the Topman's formula. The generated data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study found a positive relationship between the three independent variables of the study (Covid-19, herdsmen attack on farmers and IPOB sit-at-home order) and food availability in south east, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends a peaceful and lasting resolution to the IPOB and herders-farmers crisis in Nigeria.

Keywords: Covid-19, Sit-at-Home, Herdsmen-Attack, Food and Availability.

Introduction

The south Eastern part of Nigeria is very unique in the development process of the country. This is base on the fact that the people of the region are into different occupation, including agriculture. The region basically is comprised of Abia,

Ebonyi, Enugu, Imo and Anambra State. This region, before now is known to be very industrious in almost every sectors of life. However, recent happenings around the region has shown that more than 50% of what they eat in terms of agricultural produce (food) come from outside the region especially from the northern part of

the country. That is why it is very easy for the region to be affected whenever situations change. Basically, the challenges comprises issues of Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) disturbances like sit at home, the challenges of covid-19, and the Fulani-headsmen attack on farmers.

According to Okeke (2020) some farmers do not go to farm on Mondays because of the indigenous people of Biafra (IPOB) sit at home. The challenges of covid brought restriction of movement which affected both farmers and marketers. More so, there are some report of Fulani-heads men attack on farmers in some communities in Enugu, Ebonyi, and Imo states. Arising from these challenges that result from attacks on farmers by herders and subsequent retaliations by farmers, there was stoppage of food supplies from Northern Nigeria to South East Nigeria (Taiwo-Obalonye, 2011).The Sit-at-home protest initiated by the indigenous people of Biafra (IPOB) is another situation that has also left some landmark on the economy of the region either positively or negatively. For instance, Ebonyi State which has the highest salt deposit in the country is also one of the states leading in the production of rice, yam, potatoes and cassava in Nigeria, since the introduction of this sit-at-home on Mondays and its compliance, production of these foods have continued to be unstable. The

fear alone created by this order have also stopped those who supply from outside the region from doing so on Mondays since the order was given.

Statement of the Problem

The challenges of insecurity to food security have been a thing of concern to both government and stakeholders in our society. The situation has affected not only the agricultural economy of the south east, but Nigeria in general. In considerations of these series of situations that is seriously bedeviling the Nation Nigeria and south east in particular the researchers have decided to carry out this research. The essence is to establish if these situational factors affect agricultural food availability in South East Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

Apart from the main objective of the study which is to establish relationship between situational factors (Issues) and agricultural products (food) availability in south east, Nigeria. The study is also set to achieve certain specific objectives.

Specifically, the study is set to:

- (i) examine the effect of covid-19 on food availability in south east, Nigeria.

- (ii) establish the relationship between herders attack on farmers and food availability in south east, Nigeria.
- (iii) evaluate the effect of the activities of IPOB sit-at-home order on food availability in south east, Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

According to Isinwa (2017), scope of the study covers three basic areas; the content, the geographic and the unit scope.

The content scope of the study tries to establish the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. It tries to establish if covid-19, herders attack on farmers and IPOB sit-at-home order affects the availability of food in south east, Nigeria. The geographical scope of the study is the five south eastern states of Nigeria which are; Abia, Anambra,

Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. Efforts were made to ensure that the local governments where herders have attacked farmers in the region are brought to limelight. The unit scope of the study are the users of agricultural food in south east, Nigeria. Another set of people included in the study are farmers that produce agricultural food.

Conceptual Review

Conceptual clarification is a vital factor in research of this nature, because it helps to generate clear understanding of the concepts under review. Conceptual clarification has to do with elucidation of concepts containing information about the problem under study. It is a very decisive part of every research; hence every work is conceptually reviewed for better understanding.

Figure 1 Operational Conceptual Framework

Effects of Fulani Herdsmen Attack on Availability of Food in South-East Nigeria

In Nigeria in general, Fulani herdsmen has attacked numerous agricultural communities and has killed many farmers (Egodike *et al.*, 2020). This situation has discouraged many farmers to effectively engage in farming as some of them are going into other occupations. World Health Organization (WHO) (2020) reported that many people have left their farming occupation and entered into other businesses because of insecurity. In the south east, there are cases of Fulani-herdsmen attack on communities, which has negatively affected farming.

Impact of Covid-19 on Food Availability in the South East, Nigeria

The covid 19 which affected businesses in the world also hindered agricultural activities (Okeke, 2020). Many farmers in the south east and beyond were restricted from engaging in their agricultural activities because of movement restriction (WHO, 2020). There is need for farmers to develop online measures to continue their business in case of future challenges.

Impact of IPOB Sit-at-Home Order on Food Availability in the South East

The activities of IPOB is affecting food security in the south east Nigeria. According

to Ekpo and Agorye (2019), the regular Monday sit at home and other sit at homes affect the entire businesses in the region. If the issue of food security must be achieved, the insecurity in the region must stop.

Theoretical Review

Depot Theory

Depot Theory developed by Aspinwall (1958), states that there is need to use depot to preserve goods for future use. Here, a community can achieve food security if it has depot where it can preserve food for future use. In the context of this work, with the situational issues in the south east, Nigeria such as herdsmen attack, that hinder the planting and harvesting of agricultural product, IPOB sit-at-home order and Covid-19 pandemic that hinder the transportation of agricultural products (food) from other parts of the country especially the north to the south east, there is no longer the steady flow of goods from the points of production to final consumption. Agricultural product marketers in the south east are no longer able to receive the goods they paid for from north as at when due. This is a serious problem that is causing food insecurity and set back in the availability of agricultural products in the south east, Nigeria which require urgent attention.

Empirical Review

Egodike *et al.* (2020) investigated the Clash between Farmers Herdsmen: A Threat to Food Security in South East, Nigeria. The work used primary data through survey which were analyzed using mean. It found that Farmers Herdsmen are threat to Food Security in South East, Nigeria.

Iheanacho (2017) researched on the Menace of Fulani Herdsmen in Nigeria: A Threat to National Security. The work used new data through survey which were analyzed using ANOVA and percentages. It found that Farmers Herdsmen has hindered the commitment of farmers and national food security. Okonkwo *et al.* (2021) carried out a research on Covid-19 and the Food Deficit Economy in Southeastern Nigeria. The work used questionnaire as primary data and the data were analyzed using chi-square and percentages. It found that Covid-19 affects Food security and economic development in Southeastern Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the survey method of research. The choice of survey research method is hinged on the fact that it helps in collecting data from respondents in order to determine their current opinion with respect to one or more variables (Anyanwu, 2016).

Study Area

The areas covered in this study include the five (5) states that make up the South-Eastern region of Nigeria, namely: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States.

Sample Unit

South-Easterners who are particularly affected by Covid-19 pandemic, herdsmen attacks, and IPOB's sit-at-home order are respondents for data collection in this study.

Sample Size Determination

Since the study's population is unknown, the researcher adopted the Topman's formula in determining the sample size for the study. According to Egbulonu (2000), in determining the sample size when the population is unknown, we have:

$$N = \frac{pq(z)^2}{e^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

p = probability of success

q = probability of failure

z = level of significance = 1.96

e = error level = 0.05

To determine the probability of success and failure, the researcher conducted a pilot survey on 20 respondents to know if situational issues affect agricultural food

marketing. From the responses, 16 respondents said 'yes' while the remaining said 'no,.

Hence, $p = 16/20 = 0.80$

$$q = 1 - 0.80 = 0.20$$

$$n = \frac{0.8 \times 0.2 (1.96)^2}{0.05^2} = 246 \text{ (approx.)}$$

Sampling Procedure

Both probability and non-probability sampling designs were employed in this study. The region under study were categorized in five (5) groups/states (strata). Thereafter, judgmental sampling design was used in the selection of respondents who are affected by the situational issues under study.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire to be adopted in this study will be streamlined and structured to reflect the issues under study, as well as the research objectives and hypotheses. The questionnaire is in likert-scale form.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the questionnaire responses was analyzed using frequencies and percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Research Findings and Discussion

Results

Table 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of responses to the selected situational issues

S/N	Covid-19 and Agricultural Food Marketing	Responses	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev.
1	Advent of Covid-19 has affected agricultural food marketing.	Frequency %	77 35.65	115 53.24	5 2.31	9 4.17	10 4.63	216 100	4.11	0.98
2	Users no longer buy the quantity they normally buy.	Frequency %	99 45.83	97 44.91	9 4.17	10 4.63	1 0.46	216 100	4.31	0.80
3	Covid-19 lockdown led to both user and seller scarcity.	Frequency %	6 2.78	84 38.89	5 2.31	110 50.93	11 5.09	216 100	2.83	1.09
4	During covid-19, emphasis shifted from economy to health.	Frequency %	36 16.67	86 39.81	0 0.00	86 39.81	8 3.70	216 100	3.26	1.25
Herdsmen attack and agricultural food marketing			SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev.
5	The attack on farmers by herdsmen affects agricultural food marketing.	Frequency %	127 58.80	84 38.89	0 0.00	4 1.85	1 0.46	216 100	4.54	0.65
6	Herdsmen attack on farmers leads to low productivity.	Frequency %	43 19.91	45 20.83	0 0.00	102 47.22	26 12.04	216 100	2.89	1.40
7	It is an issue that affects both the herders and the indigenous farmers.	Frequency %	35 16.20	13 6.02	6 2.78	123 56.94	39 18.06	216 100	2.45	1.31
8	Users of these agricultural foods hardly see them to buy.	Frequency %	39 18.06	73 33.80	95 43.98	5 2.31	4 1.85	216 100	3.64	0.87
IPOB sit-at-home order and agricultural food marketing			SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev.
9	Number of working days have reduced as a result of the order.	Frequency %	146 67.59	61 28.24	4 1.85	4 1.85	1 0.46	216 100	4.61	0.67
10	The sit-at-home order did not affect the output of farmers.	Frequency %	6 2.78	10 4.63	17 7.87	155 71.76	28 12.96	216 100	2.13	0.79
11	There is panic buying in the	Frequency	101	81	11	13	10	216	4.16	1.08

12	affected area.	%	46.76	37.50	5.09	6.02	4.63	100	3.51	1.39	
	So many people are thinking of relocating which also affected business in the area.	Frequency	69	62	19	43	23	216			
		%	31.94	28.70	8.80	19.91	10.65	100			
Effect of situational factors on food availability in South East			Responses	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Std Dev.
13	Situational issues affect food availability in South East.	Frequency	164	43	4	4	1	216	4.69	0.65	
		%	75.93	19.91	1.85	1.85	0.46	100			
14	Agricultural food is scarce in South East.	Frequency	11	17	32	132	24	216	2.35	0.96	
		%	5.09	7.87	14.81	61.11	11.11	100			
15	Unavailability of food in the area within this period can be traced to the issues at hand.	Frequency	11	19	0	142	44	216	2.13	1.00	
		%	5.09	8.80	0.00	65.74	20.37	100			
16	The situational issues in South East prevent sellers from conveying foods to the area.	Frequency	17	106	26	52	15	216	3.27	1.12	
		%	7.87	49.07	12.04	24.07	6.94	100			

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Discussion

A total of 77 respondents representing 35.65% strongly agreed, while 115 respondents representing 53.24% agreed that the advent of Covid-19 affected agricultural food marketing and people no longer buy the food quantity they normally buy (45.83% strongly agreed while 44.91% agreed). This finding is corroborated by the findings of Amare *et al.* (2020); Andam *et al.* (2020) and Balana *et al.* (2020) who found that Covid-19 worsened the exposure to food insecurity in several Nigerian households. Another reason for food scarcity during covid-19 in south east, Nigeria was due to border closures (Munonye *et al.*, 2022). Also, it was also found that emphasis shifted from economy to health during Covid-19 (16.67% strongly agreed while 39.81% agreed) in south east, Nigeria. However, 50.93% disagreed while 5.09% strongly disagreed that Covid-19 lockdown led to both buyer and seller scarcity. Thus Covid-19, did not cause the

scarcity of buyers and sellers but led to shortage in food supply. It was found that 58.80% of the respondents strongly agreed while 38.89% of the respondents agreed that the attack on farmers by herdsmen affected agricultural food marketing and buyers hardly see these agricultural foods to buy (18.06% strongly agreed while 33.80% agreed). As such, herders and farmers clash contributed largely to limited food availability in the study area. Due to the sit-at-home order by IPOB, the number of working days reduced according to respondents (67.59% strongly agreed while 28.24% agreed). Also, it triggered panic buying in the affected areas (46.76% strongly agreed and 37.50% agreed) while majority of the respondents opined that the sit-at-home order did not affect the output of farmers (71.76 disagreed while 12.96 strongly disagreed). The findings of this study on the impact of sit-at-home in south east, Nigeria is consistent with the submission of (Alita, 2023) that

disruptions in the food supply potentially results in declined food quality, creates food shortages which impacts eventually lead to higher food prices.

Conclusion

This study concludes that Covid-19, herdsman attack on farmers and IPOB sit-at-home order all individually reduced food supply and availability in south east, Nigeria. However, Covid-19, herdsman attack on farmers and IPOB sit-at-home order did not cause the scarcity of buyers and sellers.

Recommendations

In line with the conclusion above the researcher recommends the following.

1. The government of the country should intervene in terms proffering a lasting peaceful resolution to this herders-farmers clash that have lasted so long in the country.
2. To curb the tension and negative impact of IPOB's sit-at-home in south east, this study suggests a purposeful dialogue between the IPOB and federal government of Nigeria.
3. It was recommended that the government of south east states should set-up a coordinated

approach to handle issues of nomadic farmers in the region.

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